

Characterization for ablation properties of thermal protection composites

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SUMMARY

To investigate the ablation/denudation/erosion characteristics of thermal protection composites (TPC) ground test and numerical simulation were used. The results show that numerical simulation was in good agreement with experimental data. We find that line ablation rates of TPC will markedly increase under the condition of existing particles in the flow field.

Keywords: Thermal protection composites, Ground Test, Numerical Simulation

HEADINGS

TPC have been taken more attentions for their unique properties in the aerospace fields. In which the ablation of TPC is more important. The ablation of TPC involves not only the thermo-chemistry ablation due to aero-heating, but also the denudation due to aero-shear force and erosion caused by atom in the atmosphere striking the surface of materials, all above effects makes that the investigation on ablation properties of TPC under the service environment to a complicated problem due to it related to mechanics, chemistry and heat transfer. The theoretical investigations on coupled properties of TPC among ablation, denudation and erosion were conducted by Landau, Soo and Ren Fen et al use a corresponding theoretical model to analyze the same problem were present^[1-3]. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model evaluating ablation properties of Carbon/Carbon composites was established by Ryan Grosse^[4], in which a meso-scale ablative model was proposed using numerical simulation on the ablation properties. In experimental aspect, some plasma wind tunnel facilities were used for investigate the ablation properties of TPC were reported by NASA, CORIA Research Center in France and the University of Stuttgart in Germany, respectively^[5-7]. Even though much works related to the field for TPC ablation property were done, the theoretical and experimental results match not so well. In this paper, a numerical model for ablation/denudation coupling characteristics of material is proposed with the aid of finite element method (FEM). Furthermore, a numerical code corresponding to the model has been made. In addition, the experiments were implemented to study the phenomena of ablation/denudation in the ground facility. Results of numerical simulation are validated through experiments.

Experiments were also carried out to investigate coupled properties among ablation, denudation and erosion.

1. Numerical simulation on ablative propriety

The ablation properties of TPC can be characterized by the ablation rate. The ablation rate can be expressed as^[8-9]

$$\dot{m}_{-\infty} = \dot{m}_{wc} + \dot{m}_{wt} \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{m}_{-\infty}$ is the total mass ablation rate, \dot{m}_{wc} is the thermo-chemistry ablation rate, and \dot{m}_{wt} is the mass loss rate due to mechanical denudation. The factor of mechanical denudation is defined as:

$$f_r = \frac{\dot{m}_{-\infty}}{\dot{m}_{wc}} \quad (2)$$

Considering mechanical denudation, the ablation rate of composite can be written

$$\dot{m}_{-\infty} = f_r \dot{m}_{wc} \quad (3)$$

Here, the factor of mechanical denudation f_r should be determined by experiment.

In order to calculate of the thermo-chemistry ablation rate \dot{m}_{wc} , the effective mass concentration \tilde{C}_{kw} and the effective diffuse flux rate \tilde{J}_{kw} are introduced

$$\tilde{C}_{kw} = \sum_{i=1}^p m_{ki} C_{iw} \quad (4)$$

$$\tilde{J}_{kw} = \sum_{i=1}^p m_{ki} J_{iw} \quad (5)$$

In equation (4) and (5), m_{ki} is mass fraction of k element in i specie, C_{iw} is mass concentration of i specie at wall, J_{iw} is diffuse flux rate of i specie at wall, and the expression for J_{iw} is given by

$$J_{iw} = \rho_i D_{ij} \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial y} \quad (6)$$

where ρ_i is the density of i specie and D_{ij} is double-species diffuse coefficient for i specie and j specie.

The mass conservation equation of k element at wall, can be given as:

$$\tilde{J}_{kw} + (\rho v)_w \tilde{C}_{kw} = \dot{m}_s \tilde{C}_{ks} \quad (7)$$

where \tilde{C}_{ks} is mass concentration of k element at inner wall.

Combining the equations above, the thermo-chemistry ablative rate of TPC can be determined.

FEM simulation have been conducted to evaluate coupled characteristics of ablation/denudation for TPC. The results of simulations are shown in figures (1), (2) and (3).

Fig. 1: Sample's Temperature field

Fig. 2: Coupled thermo-mechanics stress field

Fig. 3: Surface Temperature of test sample

3. Ground Test

3.1 Ground testing for the coupled ablation/denudation characteristics.

In the servicing condition, not only the thermo-chemistry ablation can appear on the surface of TPC caused by aero heating, but also the lamellar or graininess desquamation may happen on the material's surface due to aero-shear force, also called "denudation" phenomena. When thermo-chemistry ablation occurs, remarkable roughness change of surface is found in woven composite due to its particular weave structure. Since the "denudation" occurs easily on rough surface under external aero-shear force, it is crucial to investigate "denudation" phenomena in weave composite.

Heating facility can provide a flow field with high pressure at stagnation point and high enthalpy is required in the research of the coupled ablation/denudation characteristics for weave composites. In this paper, experiments are carried out based on three-phase voltaic plasmas arc heater, which can provide needed flow field parameters. Stagnation point tests are conducted with a testing condition (Heat flux at stagnation point is 10MW/m^2 , Pressure at stagnation point is 0.98kPa , Enthalpy is 5MJ/kg). Samples for the tests are flat-face cylinder with a 20mm in diameter. During testing, the evolvational information such as the surface temperature of the samples, meso feature of ablation surface, the real-time line ablative rate and the emission spectrums of ablation are measured. Ablation property of TPC is characterized using the information of the samples' line ablative rate.

Fig. 4: Arc heater

Fig.5: Sample for the tests

The high speed CCD with high resolution is used to monitor the line ablative rate and meso feature of ablation surface. The results are shown in the fig. 6 and fig. 7.

Fig. 6: Ablation surface

Fig. 7: Line ablative rate

Fig. 8: Roughness of surface after testing

Fig. 9: SEM photo of fiber bundle

In Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, the roughness of surface and SEM photo of fiber bundle after testing are shown, respectively. It can be seen that, under relatively high pressure at stagnation point in the flow field, the denudation is obviously observed. This is mainly caused by Z orientation fiber bundle breaking off and peeling off from the surface under the aero-shear force.

With the factor of mechanical denudation f_r , determined by experiment, numerical computation is carried out for determining the coupled ablation rate of TPC. The results are shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10 Numerical prediction results

As shown in Fig. 11, the agreements between numerical and experimental results are good within the error rate of less than 9%.

Fig.11 Comparison between numerical and experimental results

3.2 Ground testing for the coupled properties among ablation, denudation and erosion

During the service process for the TPC, solid or liquid particles in the flow field can erode and impact on ablation surface, and those can affect material ablation characteristics such as increasing the ablation surface roughness. For studying the ablation characteristics of the TPC during ablation, denudation and erosion, experiments based on arc heater are carried out. Stagnation point tests are conducted with a testing condition (Heat flux at stagnation point is 10MW/m^2 , Pressure at stagnation point is 0.98MPa , Enthalpy is 5MJ/kg). Moreover, the erosion is simulated through adding appropriate solid particles (particle size is $150\mu\text{m}$, particle speed $<1.4\text{Ma}$) into flow field. Samples for the tests are flat-face cylinder with a 20mm in diameter.

The surface temperature, ablation surface micro-topography, sample real-time line ablation rate and ablation emission spectrums of sample are monitored. Ablation property of TPC are characterized through the information of the samples' line ablative rate.

The micro-topography of the sample's ablation surface after test are observed by SEM. The results indicate that particles in the flow field can severely damage the material ablation surface. Fig.12(A) and Fig.12(B) show the images of fiber and interphase damaged by particles.

Fig.12: (A) Image of fiber on the; ablation surface

(B) Image of interphase on ablation surface

Erosion of particles in the flow field seriously affect material ablation surface roughness and mechanical property. For this reason, the thermo-chemical ablation and denudation become more seriously. Fig.14 gives the comparison of the curve of TPC ablation surface temperature vs. time for the presence of particles and the absence of particles under the situation of the same material parameter and the flow field circumstance by arc heater. The effect of particles in the flow field on TPC material ablation speed is given in Fig.15

Fig.14: The effect of particles in the flow field on TPC ablation surface temperature

Fig. 15: The effect of particles in the flow field on TPC material ablation speed

4. Conclusions

Numerical code has been accomplished for simulating the coupled ablation/denudation characteristics of TPC, and ground simulation tests were conducted for the same purposes. Further, the numerical results have been validated by the experimental results. Experimental investigations on the coupled properties of TPC among ablation, denudation and erosion were proposed with the adding of appropriate particles into the flow field. The main conclusions are as follows:

- (1) Numerical simulation for the coupled ablation/denudation characteristics of TPC by FEM and numerical program were performed, which showed good agreements between numerical and experimental results within the error rate of less than 9%. Moreover, the reliability of numerical code has been confirmed.
- (2) Under the condition of flow field with high pressure at stagnation point and high enthalpy, the coupled ablation/denudation characteristics of woven composites were presented by coarse loss caused by roughness of surface resulting from the thermo-chemistry ablation along Z-orientation of the fiber bundle.
- (3) With the adding of appropriate solid particles into the flow field, the surface erosion became severe and the ablative surface roughness increased, which led to remarkable increasing of denudation and of surface temperature of TPC.

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